

Assessment of Vegetation Condition in Lower Narmada Basin Using Remote Sensing and GIS

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ABSTRACT

The study employs remote sensing and GIS to evaluate vegetation conditions in the Lower Narmada Basin. This study calculates numerous spectral indices using Landsat data from 2015, 2020 and 2025, including the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI). The research revealed patterns in vegetation cover, water content, moisture levels, and built-up areas throughout the basin. The study shows that there is a substantial relationship between NDVI and NDWI, implying that vegetation expansion and water body loss occur concurrently. Furthermore, increased urbanization is associated with lower NDVI and NDMI, emphasizing the importance of balanced land management measures for ensuring ecological sustainability.

Keywords: Vegetation Condition, Remote Sensing and GIS, Landsat data, Water Index (NDWI), Built-up Index (NDBI)

INTRODUCTION

Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a widely used remote sensing technique for mapping land use and land cover (LULC) categories. This method helps in identifying different vegetation types and their health status (Tiwari et al. 2017). In the discipline of remote sensing applications, scientists have created vegetation indices to qualitatively and quantitatively evaluate vegetative cover using spectral measurements. The spectral response of vegetated regions is a complicated combination of plant, soil brightness, environmental impacts, shadow, soil colour, and moisture. Furthermore, the VI is influenced by atmospheric fluctuations, both geographical and temporal, during forty vegetation indices have been established during the last two decades to improve vegetation responsiveness while minimizing the effects of the elements mentioned above (Bannari, et. al., 1995) Many river basins, investments in water infrastructure for urban, industrial, and agricultural growth are approaching or exceeding the amount of renewable water available. This over commitment of water resources is caused by disregard for environmental water requirements,

incomplete hydrological knowledge, fuzzy water rights, and politically motivated projects with weak economic rationale, resulting in overbuilt river basins. The challenge for agricultural water management is to do more with less water in already stressed river basins, as well as to provide much stricter scrutiny by decision makers and civil society of new infrastructure development in relatively open river basins, in order to avoid over commitment (Molle, et. al., 2013).

STUDY AREA

India is a home to an extensive rivers network, with a total annual discharge of about 1,953 km³ (Gupta et.al. 2020). The Narmada River is the fifth-largest in India and the largest in Gujarat, spanning a total length of 1,312 km, often referred to as the lifeline of Central India, it flows through the Narmada River Basin, which extends between 72°32' to 81°45'E longitude and 21°20' to 23°45'N latitude, covering an area of 98,796 km² (Oza et.al, 2025). The Lower basin has major part of Gujarat state and has costal area, it covers the districts like Bharuch, Narmada, Vadodara and Choota Udaipur (Bhargav et.al. 2024). The upper hilly regions of the basin receive higher annual

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rainfall (1400-1650 mm), which causes floods in the downstream area even though it is a semiarid zone. The number of large tributaries in the lower basin of the Narmada River is smaller than that in the upper

and middle basin, however major tributaries of Narmada are Orsang, Heran and Karjan. (<https://sites.iitgn.ac.in/cnarmada/assets/files/Report.pdf>).

Study Area Map

Fig 2.1 Study area map of Narmada basin (a) India state map covered by the basin (b) Basin map showing lower sub-basin (c) lower sub-basin with Taluka boundary.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Vector data used

Narmada basin boundaries for the present study has been download from the HydroBASINS dataset which is a section of HydroSHEDS data, available at <https://www.hydrosheds.org/> (Lehner &, Grill, 2013). Further the Lower basin of the Narmada River was clipped form the main river basin using the reference

maps of Water Resources Information System- WRIS (<http://www.india-wris.nrsc.gov.in.>) through QGIS Software.

3.2 Raster data used

Cloud free Images for 3 years 2015, 2020 and 2025 has been downloaded from USGS Earth portal (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1 Landsat data used in the study

Seen	Path	Row	Sensor	Years of imagery
Seen 1	148	45	OLI	January 2015
Seen 2 Upper	147	44		January 2020
Seen 2 Lower	147	45		January 2025
Seen 3 Upper	146	44		
Seen 3 Lower	146	45		

3.3 Spectral indices calculation for vegetation status analysis

For the study various spectral indices were utilized to access the vegetation condition of Lower Narmada basin. Specifically, the like Normalized Difference

Vegetation Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDB), NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index) and NDBI (Normalized Difference built-up Index) were computed following the methodologies outlined by Kshetri, 2018 and Malik et. al., 2020. Upon calculation, the spectral index

images underwent image processing, wherein each index was classified into five classes: Very Low, Low, Moderate, High, and Very High. Subsequently an area-based statistical report was generated, facilitating the assessment of vegetation change over

time. Followed by preparation of maps (Fig 3.1). For the present study software QGIS version 3.40 has been used to process both raster and vector data.

Fig 3.1 Outline Workflow of the present study

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Normalized Difference Vegetation Cover (NDVI)

The analysis of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) over three consecutive year 2015, 2020 and 2025 reveals distinct trends in vegetation coverage across the lower Narmada basin (Fig 4.1).

Fig 4.1 Area of NDVI for years 2015, 2020 & 2025

With an NDVI coverage of 5085.98 sq. km, Class 3 has the largest area across all three years, significantly higher than the other classes. Class 2 shows a decreasing trend in area over the years. Class 1 and Class 5 have relatively small areas compared to the other classes and show a slight increasing trend. Class

4 fluctuates in area, increasing from 2015 to 2020 and then decreasing slightly in 2025.

4.2 Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

The analysis of Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) over three consecutive years 2015, 2020 and

2025 reveals distinct trends in water content across the lower Narmada basin (Fig 4.2).

Fig 4.2 Area of NDWI for years 2015, 2020 & 2025

With an NDWI coverage, Class 3 has the largest area over the course of the three years. Over time, class 2 has a declining tendency in area. Compared to the other classes, Class 1 and Class 5 have comparatively small areas and exhibit a little upward trend. Class 4 area varies, staying the same from 2015 and 2020 before somewhat growing in 2025.

4.3 Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)

The analysis of Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) over three consecutive years 2015, 2020 and 2025 reveals distinct trends in moisture content (Fig 4.3).

Fig 4.3 Area of NDMI for years 2015, 2020 & 2025

With an NDMI coverage over time, Class 3 exhibits a notable expansion in area, emerging as the leading class by 2025. Class 2 exhibits a notable decline in area over time. The area of Class 1 drastically shrinks, becoming insignificant by 2025. Between 2015 and 2020, Class 4 area somewhat increased, and in 2025, it slightly decreased.

4.4 Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI)

The analysis of Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) over three consecutive years 2015, 2020 & 2025 reveals distinct trends in build-up area across the lower Narmada Basin (Fig 4.4).

Fig. 4.4 Area of NDBI for years 2015, 2020 & 2025

With an NDBI coverage of above-mentioned area, in all three years, Class 3 has the greatest area, though it shows a minor gain in 2025 after declining from 2015 to 2020. The area of Class 2 gradually grows over time. The area of Class 4 shows a notable growth between 2015 and 2020, followed by a decline in

2025. In contrast Class 1 and Class 5 have smaller spaces than the other classes. Class 1 displays a modest rise from 2015 to 2020, followed by a decline in 2025. In class 5, there is a rise from 2015 to 2020 and a fall in 2025

Table 4.1 Correlations between the vegetation indices (NDVI, NDWI, NDMI, and NDBI) over the years 2015, 2020, and 2025

Index	NDVI (Vegetation Cover)	NDWI (Water Content)	NDMI (Moisture Content)	NDBI (Built-Up Area)
NDVI		Positive correlation	Moderate correlation	Inverse correlation
	Increasing trend	Higher NDWI supports higher NDVI, but declining NDWI may stress vegetation.	Higher NDMI indicates moisture availability supporting vegetation.	Increasing NDBI leads to decreasing NDVI due to urban expansion.
NDWI	Positive correlation		Moderate correlation	Inverse correlation
	NDVI increase suggests vegetation benefiting from water availability.	Declining in some areas, stable in others	Higher NDWI suggests better moisture retention.	Urban expansion (NDBI) leads to reduced water bodies.
NDMI	Moderate correlation	Moderate correlation		Inverse correlation
	Higher NDMI helps sustain vegetation.	NDWI decline often leads to NDMI reduction due to less water availability.	Increasing in some areas, decreasing in others	Urban growth reduces soil moisture, decreasing NDMI.
NDBI	Inverse correlation	Inverse correlation	Inverse correlation	
	Increasing NDBI means urbanization replacing vegetation.	Urban expansion reduces water bodies.	More built-up area reduces moisture retention.	Fluctuates over time with urban expansion and redevelopment

4.5 Maps of the Vegetation Indices

CONCLUSION

Important information about the environmental and land use changes in the Lower Narmada Basin can be

gained by analysing the four indices: The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), and Normalized

Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) for the years 2015, 2020, and 2025. A strong correlation between NDVI and NDWI are found in the analysis, suggesting that vegetation growth and water body decline occur at the same time. While NDVI decreases in Class 2, potentially indicating water loss, it exhibits an upward tendency, particularly in Class 3, indicating better vegetation. The inverse link between NDVI and NDBI indicates urban expansion, with 2020's Class 4 NDBI showing densification. Moisture content is measured by NDMI, which has an inverse relationship with NDBI and a minor association with NDVI. While better vegetation causes the NDMI to rise in Class 3, its decrease in Classes 1 and 2 points to urbanization-related moisture loss. The fragile balance between ecological sustainability and urban growth is highlighted by these phenomena. The interaction of these indices emphasizes how dynamically land use is changing in the Lower Narmada Basin. While expanding urbanization and decreasing water coverage provide sustainability issues, but rise in vegetation indicates favourable ecological shifts. To maintain ecological stability in the area, future land management plans should prioritize striking a balance between vegetation restoration, water conservation, and urban growth

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